

The European Nanotechnology Community Informatics Platform: Bridging data and disciplinary gaps for industry and regulators

Grant Agreement No 731032

Deliverable Report

Deliverable	D15.1: Delivery of successful User access to up to 5 user micro-projects
Work Package	WP15: UCD TA
Delivery date	M54 - 30 June 2022
Lead Beneficiary	National University of Ireland - University College Dublin (UCD)
Nature of Deliverable	Other
Dissemination Level	Public

Submitted by	Konstantinos Kotsis, Vadim Zhernovkov, Boris Kholodenko, Vladimir Lobaskin (UCD)
Revised by	Name (Organisation)
Approved by	Name (Organisation)

Table of contents

Abbreviations	4
Summary	4
Introduction	5
Summary of delivered TA projects	6
NC01 - Provision of ontology terms and descriptors for modelling data	7
Application	7
Progress	7
NC08 - SmartNanoTox - Data management and curation	9
Application	9
Progress	9
NC10 - Structural alterations of allergen upon nanoparticle binding	10
Application	10
Progress	10
NC33 - Bioinformatics analysis of the transcriptomics TIO2 dataset	12
Application	12
Progress	12
NC34 - In silico characterisation and a QSAR model for in vivo lung inflammation for set of 50 SmartNanoTox materials	14
Application	14
Progress	14
Conclusions	15
Annex:	17
NC01 - Provision of ontology terms and descriptors for modelling data	17
Overview	17
NC10 - Structural alterations of allergen upon nanoparticle binding	19

Overview	19
Outcomes	21
Evaluation	21
NC33 - Bioinformatics analysis of the transcriptomics TIO2 dataset	26
Report	26
Evaluation	27
→ Questionnaire A – To be filled-in by the NanoCommons TA provider(s):	27
→ NC34 - In silico characterisation and a QSAR model for in vivo lung inflammation for set of 50 SmartNanoTox materials	31
Report	31
Evaluation	33

Abbreviations

AO - Adverse Outcome

AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathway

CG - Coarse-grained

KE - Biological Key Event (in an AOP)

MD - Molecular Dynamics

MIE - Molecule Initiating Event (in an AOP)

NP - NanoParticle

NM - Nanomaterial

PAA-peg - PolyAcrylAmide PolyEthylene Glycol-coated nanoparticles

PM - Person-Month

QSAR - Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship

RMSD - Root Mean Square Deviation

Summary

In this deliverable, we are presenting five Transnational Access (TA) projects completed by UCD during the NanoCommons project. The TA services offered by UCD concerned computational evaluation of NM properties, annotation of computational data, and prediction of NM protein corona, Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) modeling, and analysis of NM-induced adverse AOPs. The outcome of the TA projects included new models/methodologies, data reporting templates, and development of open-access software and user-friendly web services which increase the visibility and usability of the developed models. Several computational tools were integrated into the NanoCommons Knowledge Base and posted to an open source software repository. One tool has been implemented as a standalone web tool. For each TA project, we are presenting summaries of the results, along with the application forms and the evaluation forms that were completed by both UCD and the TA applicants. In the appendices of this deliverable, we are providing more details regarding the methods, the results and the software applications that were produced in each one of the TA projects.

Introduction

The NanoCommons Transnational Access (TA) programme provides nanosafety Researchers from industry, academia and regulatory bodies with the state-of-the-art NanoCommons expertise free of charge and allows them to take advantage of the NanoCommons services, facilities and knowledge to advance their work, solve problems and take their research to the next level. UCD has provided four TA projects. In one of these projects, UCD has provided service to another NanoCommons Partner (PLUS), in the four others, the services were provided to external organisations and other EU H2020 projects. TA projects were mostly completed within the duration of the NanoCommons project and this accomplishment required 18 person-months (PM) of dedicated work of UCD personnel. Details about the requested and actual duration of each of the delivered projects is presented in Table 1. The TA projects where UCD has been involved, are the following:

1. NC01 - Provision of ontology terms and descriptors for modelling data (NanoCommons partners involved: UM, UCD)
2. NC08 - SmartNanoTox - Data management and curation (NanoCommons partners involved: UoB, EwC, UCD)
3. NC10 - Structural alterations of allergen upon nanoparticle binding (NanoCommons partners involved: UCD, Biomax)
4. NC33 - Bioinformatics analysis of the transcriptomics TIO2 dataset (NanoCommons partners involved: UCD)
5. NC34 - In silico characterisation and a QSAR model for in vivo lung inflammation for set of 50 SmartNanoTox materials (NanoCommons partners involved: UCD)

Table 1: Requested and actual duration of TA projects

Transnational Access Project	Requested Duration (in Person Months)	Actual Duration (in days)	Actual Duration (in Person Months)
NC01	0	26	1.3

NC08	0	14	0.7
NC10	4.25	106	5.3
NC33	5	124	6.2
NC34	4	90	4.25
Total	13.25	360	18

UCD offered services in the following main areas:

1. Computational evaluation of NM descriptors for selected materials (NC10, NC34)
2. Data processing and annotation (NC08)
3. Development of ontology terms and MODA descriptor sheets (NC01)
4. Transcriptomics data processing and prediction of KEs and MIEs (NC33)
5. Model deployment on the client computers (NC10)

Summary of delivered TA projects

The following section provides information regarding the 5 TA projects where UCD has been involved. The reader can find in the Annex a more detailed description of the TAs, along with the evaluation form that contains one or two parts: a self-evaluation part completed by UCD (the TA provider or contributor) and second part which was filled in by the TA applicant and contained an assessment of the usefulness and perceived value of the offered services and the TA outcome.

NC01 - Provision of ontology terms and descriptors for modelling data

Application

Application number	NC01
Application name	Provision of ontology terms and descriptors for modelling data
Applicant name and organisation	Alexander Lyubartsev
Link to application document	
Linked to FP7 / H2020 project	SmartNanoTox
Duration requested (<i>days</i>)	10
Starting date	Discussions since autumn 2019
Estimated end date	2021

Progress

Total duration required up to now (<i>days</i>)	46 days (distributed over a long period)
% completion	80%
Delivery dates – per partner (<i>needed for reporting in the EC portal – actual days spent</i>)	UM: 20 days UCD: 26 days
Leading NanoCommons partner and contact person	Maastricht University (UM) - Egon Willighagen, Ammar Ammar, Laurent Winckers
NanoCommons partners involved	University College Dublin (UCD) - Konstantinos Kotsis, Vladimir Lobaskin
NanoCommons services utilised	
New NanoCommons services arising from the TA	MODA templates for materials modelling
Brief summary of work done (<i>200 words</i>)	UCD has defined simulation ontology terms for quantum chemical and molecular simulations, and coarse-grained corona simulation of nanodescriptors. In particular, we have created MODAs for evaluation of electronic properties of

	<p>ENMs, such as band gap, polarizability and electronegativity, ionisation potential and electron affinity by quantum chemical semi-empirical methods, potentials of mean force for the binding energies of amino acids in water at a ENM surface by metadynamics simulation, immersion enthalpies of ENM surfaces by classical molecular dynamics simulation and adsorption energies of the proteins in the corona by coarse grained simulation. UCD team also contributed to the development of EMMC's OSMO ontology for materials modelling.</p>
<p>Main outcomes / outputs (200 words)</p>	<p>Novel templates for reporting computational materials models have been proposed. We have extended the EMMC MODA templates to (i) make them more structured and machine-readable, and (ii) include rich metadata. Usually, the metadata can be pulled in directly from simulation input files. Multiple ontology terms have been defined within ontology for simulation, modelling, and optimization (OSMO) ontology for MODA, containing the simulation methods and types as well as materials models used. This work was done in collaboration with the EMMO working group.</p> <p>https://github.com/thomasexner/Moda</p> <p>Novel ontology terms for the materials models defined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● eNanoMapper ontology Release 7 (2021-02-04, doi:10.5281/zenodo.4600986) ● eNanoMapper ontology Release 8 (2022-08-11; doi:10.5281/zenodo.6984499)
<p>Publications or other records (e.g. project newsletter articles, links on other EU project webpages etc.)</p>	<p>Semantic Interoperability and Characterization of Data Provenance in Computational Molecular Engineering, M. T. Horsch, C. Niethammer, G. Boccardo, P. Carbone, S. Chiacchiera, M. Chiricotto, J. D. Elliott, V. Lobaskin, P. Neumann, P. Schiffels, M. A. Seaton, I. T. Todorov, J. Vrabec, W. L.Cavalcanti, <i>J. Chem. Eng. Data</i> 2020, 65, 3, 1313–1329 https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jced.9b00739</p>
<p>Any follow-up activities planned? (e.g. additional TA, research collaboration)</p>	<p>The templates will be further developed and linked to EMMO / eNanoMapper ontologies.</p> <p>Manuscript in preparation: Metadata stewardship in nanosafety research: approaches to improve completeness of structured metadata reporting A. G. Papadiamantis, L. Farcas, G. Cornelis, B. Hardy, E. Valsami-Jones, I. Lynch, E. Willighagen, K. Kotsis, V. Lobaskin, T. E. Exner</p>

NC08 - SmartNanoTox - Data management and curation

Application

Application number	NC08
Application name	SmartNanoTox - Data management and curation
Applicant name and organisation	Olivier Joubert, University of Lorraine
Link to application document	
Linked to FP7 / H2020 project	SmartNanoTox
Duration requested (<i>days</i>)	70 calendar days (2.33PM)
Starting date	February 10, 2020
Estimated end date	June 30, 2020

Progress

Leading NanoCommons partner and contact person	UoB, Tassos Papadiamantis
NanoCommons partners involved	UoB, Biomax, UCD
NanoCommons services utilised	NanoCommons Knowledge Base
New NanoCommons services arising from the TA	
Total duration required up to now (<i>days</i>)	UCD: 14 (0.7 PM)
% completion	100
Delivery dates – per partner (<i>needed for reporting in the EC portal – actual days spent</i>)	UCD: September 30, 2020 - 14 days spent
Brief summary of work done (<i>200 words</i>)	Computational data for 50 ENMs generated by SmartNanoTox project were organised, processed, annotated and uploaded to NanoCommons Knowledge Base.

Main outcomes / outputs (200 words)	Computational characteristics of ENMs are available through the search interface in the NanoCommons KB organised by material and size. Novel types of ENM descriptors (e.g. protein adsorption energies) were introduced and supplemented with metadata and other materials characterisation data (potentials of mean force for interaction of biomolecular fragments with ENMs).
Any follow-up activities planned? (e.g. additional TA, research collaboration)	The datasets will be

NC10 - Structural alterations of allergen upon nanoparticle binding

Application

Application number	NC10
Application name	Structural alterations of allergen upon nanoparticle binding
Applicant name and organisation	Robert Mills-Goodlet, Ingrid Hasenkopf, Litty Johnson (PLUS)
Link to application document	
Linked to FP7 / H2020 project	International PhD Programme "Immunity in Cancer and Allergy" funded by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) under grant agreement W01213
Duration requested (days)	90
Starting date	Jan 2020
Estimated end date	Apr 2021

Progress

Total duration required up to now (days)	169
% completion	100
Delivery dates – per partner	Biomax: 63 days (30.4.22)

<i>(needed for reporting in the EC portal – actual days spent)</i>	UCD: 106 days (30.6.2022)
Leading NanoCommons partner and contact person	UCD, Vladimir Lobaskin, Ian Rouse; Biomax, Dieter Maier
NanoCommons partners involved	UCD, PLUS, Biomax
NanoCommons services utilised	UnitedAtom, NC Knowledge Base, NanoXtract
New NanoCommons services arising from the TA	
Brief summary of work done <i>(200 words)</i>	<p>The work was conducted in four stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishment of an <i>in silico</i> nanoparticle library and application of protein corona modelling 2. Synthesis, surface functionalization and physico-chemical (PC) characterization of NPs 3. Collection of experimental protein corona data 4. Annotation of (i) PC data and metadata of the synthesized differently functionalized NPs, (ii) protein corona data and metadata, and (iii) corona modeling data and metadata in the NanoCommons KB
Main outcomes / outputs <i>(200 words)</i>	<p>Work of stages 1. to 3. has been completed. From stage 4., so far, (i) PC data and metadata of the synthesized differently functionalized NPs and (iii) <i>in silico</i> protein corona modeling data and metadata have been provided for upload to the NanoCommons KB, while (ii) experimental protein corona <i>in vitro</i> data and metadata are still in process for finally establishing reporting style and format to be uploaded.</p>

Publications or other records (e.g. project newsletter articles, links on other EU project webpages etc.)	<p>This TA resulted in a publication</p> <p>Computational prediction and experimental analysis of the nanoparticle-protein corona: Showcasing an in vitro-in silico workflow providing FAIR data</p> <p>Ingrid Hasenkopf^f, Robert Mills-Goodlet¹, Litty Johnson¹, Ian Rouse², Mark Geppert¹, Albert Duschl¹, Dieter Maier³, Vladimir Lobaskin², Iseult Lynch⁴, and Martin Himly¹</p> <p>Affiliations: 1 PLUS; 2 UCD; 3 Biomax; 4 UoB Nano Today 46, 101561 (2022) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nantod.2022.101561</p>
Social media activity relating to the TA activity	<p>6 shares and comments, 11 tweets by September 20, 2022 e.g. https://twitter.com/martinhimly/status/1551496656495034369</p>
Any follow-up activities planned? (e.g. additional TA, research collaboration)	<p>Follow-up study appointed with UCD and Diego Martinez for tackling limitations identified by protein corona prediction (surface functionalization).</p>

NC33 - Bioinformatics analysis of the transcriptomics TIO2 dataset

Application

Application number	NC33
Application name	Bioinformatics analysis of the transcriptomics TIO2 dataset
Applicant name and organisation	Ulla Vogel, NRCWE
Link to application document	
Linked to FP7 / H2020 project	SmartNanoTox , Harmless
Duration requested (days)	100 calendar days (5 PM)
Starting date	November 1, 2020
Estimated end date	March 31, 2021

Progress

Total duration required up to now (days)	124 (6.2 PM)
% completion	100%
Delivery dates – per partner (needed for reporting in the EC portal – actual days spent)	UCD: June 2, 2022- 124 days spent
Leading NanoCommons partner and contact person	UCD, Boris Kholodenko
NanoCommons partners involved	UCD
NanoCommons services utilised	MIE prediction tool
New NanoCommons services arising from the TA	
Brief summary of work done (200 words)	The overall aim of the project was to identify changes in pulmonary gene expression profiles in mice exposed to four titanium dioxide nanomaterials (TiO ₂ ENMs) with different physicochemical properties by instillation. We applied a cell State Transition Assessment and Regulation (cSTAR) techniques to reveal carcinogenic ENMs among different materials including rutile TiO ₂ nanoparticles, and anatase TiO ₂ tubes. An analysis of 500 genes with top positive and 500 genes with top negative contributions to the STV was combined with the signaling network exploration to identify the genes and processes that drive carcinogenesis or suppression of tumor development.
Main outcomes / outputs (200 words)	In this project we investigated the differences in pulmonary responses after instillation by different types of TiO ₂ NMs. As input for the analysis, we provided raw files from RNA microarrays profiling. The methodology to characterise the cell State Transition Assessment and Regulation is described in a Nature paper Rukhlenko, O.S., Halasz, M., Rauch, N. et al. Control of cell state transitions. Nature (2022). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05194-y The MIE prediction tool has been described in Deliverable 5.7 and made available at https://armadillo.shinyapps.io/mies/

Publications or other records (<i>e.g. project newsletter articles, links on other EU project webpages etc.</i>)	A webinar was organised in May 2021 to present the tool to the community. Asina, Gov4Nano and other projects took part in the event Online MIE Prediction Tool Webinar
Any follow-up activities planned? (<i>e.g. additional TA, research collaboration</i>)	A manuscript on the toxicity mechanisms triggered by TiO ₂ in collaboration between UCD, NRCWE and Health Canada will be submitted in 2023.

NC34 - In silico characterisation and a QSAR model for in vivo lung inflammation for set of 50 SmartNanoTox materials

Application

Application number	NC34
Application name	In silico characterisation and a QSAR model for in vivo lung inflammation for set of 50 SmartNanoTox materials
Applicant name and organisation	Otmar Schmid, HMGU
Link to application document	
Linked to FP7 / H2020 project	SmartNanoTox
Duration requested (<i>days</i>)	80 days (4 PM)
Starting date	September 1, 2021
Estimated end date	June 30, 2022

Progress

Leading NanoCommons partner and contact person	UCD, Vladimir Lobaskin
NanoCommons partners involved	UCD
NanoCommons services utilised	United Atom software package
New NanoCommons services arising from the TA	

Total duration required up to now (days)	90 (4.25 PM)
% completion	100
Delivery dates – per partner (needed for reporting in the EC portal – actual days spent)	UCD: 90
Brief summary of work done (200 words)	We computed characteristics of 50 ENMs from the list of SmartNanoTox project using density functional theory for electronic density distribution and calculated intrinsic and extrinsic descriptors as well as bionano interaction descriptors for essential biomolecules on the surface of these ENMs via direct atomistic simulations and United Atom tool. We evaluated potentials of mean force for interaction of small biomolecules (amino acids, lipid fragments) with the selected ENMs.
Main outcomes / outputs (200 words)	The produced descriptors and potentials of mean force for titania, silica, CNT, iron oxide, graphene, carbon black ENMs have been made available via open source United Atom software package https://bitbucket.org/softmattergroup/unitedatom Computed protein adsorption energies have been uploaded to the NanoCommons KB and are available via the main KB web interface. A set of protein adsorption energies for 1135 proteins on multiple ENMs was included into a manuscript submitted to Scientific Data S. Alsharif, I. Rouse, V. Lobaskin, Computed Protein Binding Energies on Selected Nanoparticles, Sci. Data (2022) (submitted)
Publications or other records (e.g. project newsletter articles, links on other EU project webpages etc.)	The methodology and part of the data are included in publication I. Rouse, D. Power, E. G. Brandt, M. Schneemilch, K. Kotsis, N. Quirke, A. P. Lyubartsev and V. Lobaskin, First principles characterisation of bio–nano interface, Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 2021, 23, 13473 http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/d1cp01116b This paper was distinguished as PCCP Hot Article and included in the 2021 paper collection.
Any follow-up activities planned? (e.g. additional TA, research collaboration)	A manuscript is in preparation: M. Meunier, I. Rouse, A. Colibaba, K. Kotsis, A. Lyubartsev, O. Schmid, V. Lobaskin, Prediction of nanomaterial-induced in vivo lung inflammation using computational material characterisation. to be submitted in 2022.

Conclusions

Two UCD teams: Soft Matter group (V. Lobaskin, K. Kotsis, I. Rouse) and Systems Biology (B. Kholodenko, V. Zhernovkov, O. Rukhlenko) participated in 5 TA projects. All TA applicants provided positive evaluations of the TA outcomes and the delivered results and highlighted the benefits of the TA project results to different stakeholders, researchers and regulators and to the society in terms of supporting specific Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Based on the TA projects, UCD developed collaborations with several academic partners and governmental labs that will continue to evolve after the end of the NanoCommons project. Several open source software tools have been made available via NanoCommons KB, BitBucket repository and standalone web interfaces. The new ontology entries are available via EMMC WG.

Annex:

NC01 - Provision of ontology terms and descriptors for modelling data

Overview

Studies of ENM safety involve construction of statistical predictive models relating the ENM properties to the biological activities and adverse outcomes and therefore demand collection of advanced characterisation data. Some of the ENM descriptors are generated computationally using physics-based models. To combine experimental and computational data, semantic mapping and clear ontology definitions of the methods and quantities are required. In this TA, UM, 7P9 and UCD teams worked on creation of ontology terms for computational materials science. UCD teams engaged in collaboration with EMMC working group on ontologies and contributed to the first version of OSMO (Ontology for Simulation, Modelling, and Optimisation) ontology¹ that is supposed to be used with MODA descriptors of the modelling methods.

UCD team has developed several MODA files using the model proposed by Thomas Exner (7P9) (Fig. 1,2). These templates are recorded in MS Excel spreadsheets and contain rich metadata as compared to standard text-based EMMC templates. The new template includes multiple simulation settings and conditions used to generate the specific data.

¹ M. T. Horsch, C. Niethammer, G. Boccardo, P. Carbone, S. Chiacchiera, M. Chiricotto, J. D. Elliott, V. Lobaskin, P. Neumann, P. Schiffels, M. A. Seaton, I. T. Todorov, J. Vrabec, W. L. Cavalcanti, Semantic Interoperability and Characterization of Data Provenance in Computational Molecular Engineering, *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 2020, 65, 3, 1313–1329 <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jced.9b00739>

-
-

 -

 -

 -

 -

 -
-

Figure 1: Example of MODA templates for computational materials characterisation developed by UCD.

corresponds to the silica NPs synthesized and surface-functionalized at PLUS and protein adsorption calculations were performed using the set of model proteins and allergens employed experimentally. One exemplary data set is depicted below in Figures 3 and 4, depicting sample results of the protein adsorption energy calculations and the corona prediction model used in the TA. The results in Figure 3 illustrate the output of UnitedAtom at the start of the TA, while Figure 4 demonstrates the results of the model of competitive adsorption (CoronaKMC) developed using feedback from the initial results of the TA. The collaboration between experimental (PLUS) and theoretical (UCD) groups lead to an excellent agreement between the predicted and measured protein corona, demonstrating the utility of the TA.

Figure 2. Orientation-specific binding energy of Bet v 1 (PDB-ID 4A88) on silica NPs. **a** pristine SiO_2 ; **b** APTES SiO_2 ; **c** COOH SiO_2 ; **d** PTMO SiO_2 ; Zeta-potentials of particles used for modelling were determined in H_2O ; Adsorption energy reported in units of $k_B T$ (Boltzmann constant at Temperature in Kelvin).

Figure 4: Computed corona abundances for the set of four proteins binding to a silica NP, computed by UCD for PLUS as part of the TA.

Outcomes

At the GA 24 in Iceland, this TA NC10 has been selected to represent a case study for WP9 and is described as CS2 in further detail in D9.2. The current state of the work has been captured in the Periodic report 2, for further details see:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1eXCZEjCGvmPFNpZJjQXRS_2B4OlvZtCm/edit#

Furthermore, the TA led to a publication ***“Computational prediction and experimental analysis of the nanoparticle-protein corona: Showcasing an in vitro-in silico workflow providing FAIR data”*** with contributions from both PLUS and UCD on the experimental and computational components respectively. The computational interface provided by Biomax was additionally improved and upgraded as a response to issues highlighted during the TA. The initial set of computational tools for full corona prediction proved to be challenging for novice users and as such a streamlined set of scripts was developed by UCD to assist in the prediction of multi-component coronas and released as part of the UnitedAtom software repository.

Evaluation

→ Questionnaire A – To be filled-in by the NanoCommons TA provider(s):

1. TA application number: NC10
2. Name of TA applicant: Ingrid
3. Surname of TA applicant: Hasenkopf

4. Affiliation of the TA applicant: PLUS
5. Main contact from NanoCommons for the TA (NanoCommons TA provider) – Name: Vladimir Lobaskin
6. Affiliation of the NanoCommons TA provider: UCD
7. Other NanoCommons partners involved:
 - Yes Which other NanoCommons partners are involved? (*Enter the name of the organizations in text form*): Biomax
 - No
8. Kind of category of the provided service/TA:
 - Experimental Workflows Design & Implementation
 - Data Processing & Analysis
 - Data Visualisation & Predictive Toxicity
 - Data Storage & Online Accessibility
9. Discipline of the service/TA: (*Example: Safe-by-Design, In silico modelling, Data and metadata curation, ...*)
 - Toxicity prediction, hazard assessment
10. Time expected vs. real time needed for the TA:

	Lead partner (UCD)	Biomax	
Expected time (in months):	4	2	
Real time (in months):	5.3	3.06	

11. Reporting / publication of the awarded TA (including grey literature or publication on the NanoCommons Webpage):

Yes Reference: to be followed up on

No

12. Estimation of costs for this TA:

	Lead partner	Biomax	
Direct personnel costs (& related PMs)	22000	13200	
Direct costs of subcontracting (& related PMs) (if applicable)			
Other direct costs (Travel, Equipment, Other goods and services...)	900		
Based on the total cost what % add-on for the Coordination / promotion etc. by NanoCommons would be appropriate? (e.g. 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 25%)	5%		

13. Has the TA provider (NanoCommons TA expert) been involved in similar TAs?

Yes Which one(s) (TA number)?:

No

14. If YES in the previous question, would it be possible to make a guideline to standardise at least a part of the TA so potential TA applicants would be able to implement a part of the TA on their own or with minimal guidance by the experts or to get started based on the training material?

Yes Re-estimation of costs:

No

15. From your experience with this and similar TAs and other dissemination activities, how would you describe the commercial potential and the market for the used services? *(Enter your answer in text form)*

16. How relevant do you see the services for the commercial sustainability of NanoCommons? *(Select just one option)*

- Very
- Slightly
- Neutral
- Slightly not
- Not at all

As described above, supporting collaborative research is not directly providing commercial sustainability but will promote the infrastructure and increase the user base.

17. How relevant do you see the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure for the sustainability of the service/TA? *(Select just one option)*

- Very
- Slightly
- Neutral
- Slightly not
- Not at all

18. Were any *social [sustainability goals](#)* addressed directly or indirectly *(e.g. through data accessibility for re-use – see here for ways [artificial intelligence supports the SDGs](#))* by the TA?
If **YES**:

o Which SDGs have been addressed? *(More than one is possible)*

SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being → If YES, why?

The NanoCommons services were used to bring safe-by-design aspects into a ligand screening campaign to speed up the drug development process. Such collaborative research projects will also in the future be needed to guarantee good health and well-being by providing information on the safety of (nano)material and support decision making.

SDG 5: Gender Equality → If YES, why?

SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation → If YES, why?

- SDG 8: Decent work and Economic Growth → If YES, why?
- SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities → If YES, why?
- SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities → If YES, why?
- SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions → If YES, why?
- SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why?

The NanoCommons infrastructure supported the collaborative research perform in this TA. Description of the existing services with the offering of consultancy to adopt the services to new challenges provided within the TA was functioning as a matchmaking tool to bring TA applicants and NanoCommons partners together to form the optimal team.

- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? *(Enter your answer in text form)*

Supporting collaborative research with its consultancy, data and software services and acting, in general, as a matchmaking tool will clearly have an ongoing positive effect on SDG3 and SDG17 but also SDG6, SDG8 and SDG11. This will become even more important when more and more services also from third parties are integrated into the infrastructure.

19. Were any *environmental* [sustainability goals](#) addressed, directly or indirectly, by the TA? If **YES**:

- o Which SDGs have been addressed? *(More than one is possible)*
 - SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation → If YES, why?
 - SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities → If YES, why?
 - SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and production → If YES, why?
 - SDG 13: Climate action → If YES, why?
 - SDG 14: Life below water → If YES, why?
 - SDG 15: Life on Land → If YES, why?
 - SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why?
- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? *(Enter your answer in text form)*

The TA was specifically designed to address the health challenge of the COVID19 pandemic. However, the collaborative research support and the matchmaking can directly be applied to environmental question and in this way, support all SDGs above and especially SDG6, SDG14, SDG15 and SDG17.

20. Were any *economic* [sustainability goals](#) addressed, directly or indirectly, by the TA? If **YES**:

- o Which SDGs have been addressed? *(More than one is possible)*

- DG 8: Decent work and Economic Growth → If YES, why?
 - SDG 9: Industry Innovation and infrastructure → If YES, why?
 - SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and production → If YES, why?
 - SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why?
- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? *(Enter your answer in text form)*
21. If you were not able to answer the last 3 questions about the *social, environmental and economic sustainability goals* that have been addressed by the TA, would you be interested in participating in an online training on how research can support the SDGs?
- Yes
 - No
22. If you answered YES to the last question, would you be willing to pay for the offered training on utilising your research in support of the SDGs?
- Yes → Enter your contact details here (Name, Affiliation, Email address):
 - No

NC33 - Bioinformatics analysis of the transcriptomics TIO2 dataset

Report

We applied a cell State Transition Assessment and Regulation (cSTAR) techniques² to reveal carcinogenic ENMs among different ENMs (TiO₂, CNTs). cSTAR uses supervised machine learning to distinguish different states and builds a State Transition Vector (STV) to identify a path from non-carcinogenic to carcinogenic states in the molecular data space. Consequently, it classified and ranked ENMs by computing a carcinogenic score for all analyzed ENMs. The dose-responses calculated for top carcinogenic ENMs suggested that besides already well-known carcinogenic ENMs, the following ENMs are likely carcinogenic, especially at high exposure doses: three different long and straight carbon nanotubes, two short, thin and entangled carbon nanotubes, one type of rutile TiO₂ nanoparticles, and anatase TiO₂ tubes. NM401, Mitsui7, MWCNT (GSE86339_C57B16, Mitsui7, GSE29042), long carbon and asbestos nanotubes (GSE51636), NRCWE26, NRCWE001, NRCWE049 MWCNTs. An analysis of 500 genes with top positive and 500 genes with top negative contributions to the STV was combined with the signaling network exploration to identify the genes and processes that drive carcinogenesis or suppression of tumor development. Finally, further analyzing

² Rukhlenko, O.S., Halasz, M., Rauch, N. *et al.* Control of cell state transitions. *Nature* **609**, 975–985 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05194-y>

carcinogenic ENMs, as suggested by carcinogenic scores, we distinguished between different mechanisms of carcinogenesis of ENMs with different shapes, fibrous vs non-fibrous ENMs.

Evaluation

→ Questionnaire A – To be filled-in by the NanoCommons TA provider(s):

1. TA application number:
2. Name of TA applicant: Ulla Brigitte
3. Surname of TA applicant: Vogel
4. Affiliation of the TA applicant: National Research Centre for the Working Environment
Denmark
5. Main contact from NanoCommons for the TA (NanoCommons TA provider) – Name: Boris
Kholodenko / UCD
6. Affiliation of the NanoCommons TA provider: UCD
7. Other NanoCommons partners involved:
 Yes Which other NanoCommons partners are involved? (*Enter the name of the organizations in text form*):
x No
8. Kind of category of the provided service/TA:
 Experimental Workflows Design & Implementation
x Data Processing & Analysis
 Data Visualisation & Predictive Toxicity
 Data Storage & Online Accessibility
9. Discipline of the service/TA: (*Example: Safe-by-Design, In silico modelling, Data and metadata curation, ...*)
 - In silico modelling and data analysis

10. Time expected vs. real time needed for the TA:

	Lead partner	Partner 2	Partner 3	etc.
Expected time (in months):	2.5			
Real time (in months):	4.2			

11. Reporting / publication of the awarded TA (including grey literature or publication on the NanoCommons Webpage):

Yes → Reference: in preparation

No

12. Estimation of costs for this TA:

	Lead partner	Partner 2	Partner 3	etc.
Direct personnel costs (& related PMs)	20000			
Direct costs of subcontracting (& related PMs) (if applicable)				
Other direct costs (Travel, Equipment, Other goods and services...)				
Based on the total cost, what % add-on for the Coordination / promotion etc. by NanoCommons would be appropriate? (e.g. 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 25%)	5%			

13. Has the TA provider (NanoCommons TA expert) been involved in similar TAs?

Yes → Which one(s) (TA number)?:

x| No

14. If YES in the previous question, would it be possible to make a guideline to standardise at least a part of the TA so potential TA applicants would be able to implement a part of the TA on their own or with minimal guidance by the experts or to get started based on the training material?

Yes → Re-estimation of costs:

No

15. From your experience with this and similar TAs and other dissemination activities, how would you describe the commercial potential and the market for the used services? (*Enter your answer in text form*)

Scientifically, this is a breakthrough, the commercial potential and the market for the used services is unclear.

16. How relevant do you see the services for the commercial sustainability of NanoCommons? (*Select just one option*)

Very

Slightly

x Neutral

Slightly not

Not at all

17. How relevant do you see the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure for the sustainability of the service/TA? (*Select just one option*)

Very

Slightly

x Neutral

Slightly not

Not at all

18. Were any *social [sustainability goals](#)* addressed directly or indirectly (*e.g. through data accessibility for re-use – see here for ways [artificial intelligence supports the SDGs](#)*) by the TA?
If YES:

- o Which SDGs have been addressed? (*More than one is possible*)
 - SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being → If YES, why?
 - SDG 5: Gender Equality → If YES, why?
 - SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation → If YES, why?
 - SDG 8: Decent work and Economic Growth → If YES, why?
 - SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities → If YES, why?
 - SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities → If YES, why?
 - SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions → If YES, why?
 - x SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why? The TA has promoted the collaboration between National Research Centre for the Working Environment Denmark and UCD

- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? (*Enter your answer in text form*)

19. Were any *environmental* [sustainability goals](#) addressed, directly or indirectly, by the TA? If

YES:

- o Which SDGs have been addressed? (*More than one is possible*)
 - SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation → If YES, why?
 - SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities → If YES, why?
 - SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and production → If YES, why?
 - SDG 13: Climate action → If YES, why?
 - SDG 14: Life below water → If YES, why?
 - SDG 15: Life on Land → If YES, why?
 - SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why?

- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? (*Enter your answer in text form*)

20. Were any *economic* [sustainability goals](#) addressed, directly or indirectly, by the TA? If **YES:**

- o Which SDGs have been addressed? (*More than one is possible*)
 - SDG 8: Decent work and Economic Growth → If YES, why?
 - SDG 9: Industry Innovation and infrastructure → If YES, why?
 - SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and production → If YES, why?
 - SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why?

- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? (*Enter your answer in text form*)

21. If you were not able to answer the last 3 questions about the *social, environmental and economic sustainability goals* that have been addressed by the TA, would you be interested in participating in an online training on how research can support the SDGs?

Yes

No

22. If you answered YES to the last question, would you be willing to pay for the offered training on utilising your research in support of the SDGs?

Yes → Enter your contact details here (Name, Affiliation, Email address):

No

→ NC34 - In silico characterisation and a QSAR model for in vivo lung inflammation for set of 50 SmartNanoTox materials

Report

In silico material characterization provides valuable information on the ENM properties that may not be readily available from experiments. Yet, due to principal technical limitations such as the large required system size or time scale, the ab initio computations at the nanoscale cannot reach the relevant system sizes and timescales. We therefore use multiscale computational techniques developed by UCD³ to generate the information about ENM properties that might be predictive of the biological activity of the materials.

In our calculations of intrinsic properties of SmartNanoTox ENMs, we used common quantum mechanical methods on the respective bulk materials. A variety of descriptors were calculated including

- Band gap [eV]
- Heat of formation [kcal/mol]
- Absolute hardness

³ I. Rouse, D. Power, E. G. Brandt, M. Schneemilch, K. Kotsis, N. Quirke, A. P. Lyubartsev and V. Lobaskin, First principles characterisation of bio–nano interface, Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 2021, 23, 13473, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/d1cp01116b>

- Electronegativity
- Dispersion energy per atom [kcal/mol]
- Dipole moment [Debye]
- Polarizability per atom [au]
- HOMO [eV]
- LUMO [eV]
- |HOMO - LUMO| [eV]
- Ionization potential [eV]
- Electron affinity [eV]
- Electrophilicity
- Chemical potential [kcal/mol]

We used DFT and DFTB, and semi-empirical methods (SIESTA, DFTB, MOPAC). The DFT and DFTB band gap results show the trend consistent with experiments, while semi-empirical calculations predict the opposite trend. For the ionization potential, the semi-empirical calculations give the trend consistent with experiments, while both DFT and DFTB show larger values for some ENMs.

In the evaluation of extrinsic properties of ENMs, such as interaction with water, lipids and proteins, we used the atomistic MD simulations and existing force fields. Specifically, the following new descriptors were proposed⁴

- Immersion enthalpy in water [kcal/mol]
- Immersion enthalpy in octanol [kcal/mol]
- logP-Nano
- Amino-acid adsorption energies [kcal/mol]
- Protein adsorption energies [kcal/mol]
- Hamaker constants [kcal/mol]

The stronger binding of proteins to ENM surfaces correlates with the weaker binding of water, as seen from the heats of immersion. The observed trends for the protein binding energies here are in agreement with known experiments. The computed binding affinities of amino acids/proteins and lipids to ENMs will be further used to predict in vitro and in vivo biological activity of ENMs. The usefulness of these descriptors has been confirmed in another study involving transcriptomics data⁵.

The statistical modelling demonstrates that the computationally generated descriptors are predictive of the biological activity of the ENMs in vivo. In particular, they correlate with the degree of inflammation (neutrophil count in lung) (Fig. 5). A manuscript is currently in preparation based on these modelling results.

⁴ Wyrzykowska, E., Mikolajczyk, A., Lynch, I. *et al.* Representing and describing nanomaterials in predictive nanoinformatics. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **17**, 924–932 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-022-01173-6>

⁵ Giudice, G. del, *et al.* A gene regulation model reveals an ancestral adaptation response to particulate exposure triggered by nanomaterials <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1547187/v1>

Figure 5. Measured and predicted neutrophil cell count in broncho-alveolar liquid of exposed mice base on SmartNanoTox data and computed descriptors.

The set of descriptors provided by UCd in this TA is by no means definitive but are selected as a set of reasonably simple properties that can be evaluated using standard computational techniques and can be employed to further characterize the surface. As an example, we note that the binding energies calculated here may be of use in estimating the composition of the protein corona which forms around a NP by using these as input for simple models of the steady-state corona. It was also used in NC10. They may additionally be of use for machine-learning models of more complex phenomena such as uptake by cells, as they provide a quantitative means to encode the chemical identity of the NP. In this work, we have presented results for titanium dioxide as this is a particularly important nanomaterial and is being extensively investigated by toxicological studies, however, we stress that the methodology we used is completely general and can be applied to a wide range of ENMs. Likewise, the range of biomolecules that can be evaluated can readily be extended by identifying further basic structures and generating PMFs and Hamaker constants for these. Our general methodology can be straightforwardly adapted to other nanomaterials, enabling their in-depth characterization and prediction of their interactions with a range of biomolecules.

Evaluation

→ **Questionnaire A – To be filled-in by the NanoCommons TA provider(s):**

1. TA application number: NC34
2. Name of TA applicant: Otmar
3. Surname of TA applicant: Schmid
4. Affiliation of the TA applicant: HMGU

5. Main contact from NanoCommons for the TA (NanoCommons TA provider) – Name: Vladimir Lobaskin

6. Affiliation of the NanoCommons TA provider: UCD

7. Other NanoCommons partners involved:

Yes Which other NanoCommons partners are involved? (Enter the name of the organizations in text form):

No

8. Kind of category of the provided service/TA:

Experimental Workflows Design & Implementation

Data Processing & Analysis

Data Visualisation & Predictive Toxicity

Data Storage & Online Accessibility

9. Discipline of the service/TA: (Example: Safe-by-Design, In silico modelling, Data and metadata curation, ...)

In silico modelling

10. Time expected vs. real time needed for the TA:

	Lead partner	Partner 2	Partner 3	etc.
Expected time (in months):	4			
Real time (in months):	4.5			

11. Reporting / publication of the awarded TA (including grey literature or publication on the NanoCommons Webpage):

Yes → Reference:

No

12. Estimation of costs for this TA:

	Lead partner	Partner 2	Partner 3	etc.
Direct personnel costs (& related PMs)	20000			
Direct costs of subcontracting (& related PMs) (if applicable)	-			
Other direct costs (Travel, Equipment, Other goods and services...)	-			
Based on the total cost what % add-on for the Coordination / promotion etc. by NanoCommons would be appropriate? (e.g. 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 25%)	5%			

13. Has the TA provider (NanoCommons TA expert) been involved in similar TAs?

Yes → Which one(s) (TA number)?:

No

14. If YES in the previous question, would it be possible to make a guideline to standardise at least a part of the TA so potential TA applicants would be able to implement a part of the TA on their own or with minimal guidance by the experts or to get started based on the training material?

Yes → Re-estimation of costs:

No

15. From your experience with this and similar TAs and other dissemination activities, how would you describe the commercial potential and the market for the used services?

Materials modelling and characterisation activities have a significant commercial potential and similar methods and codes are included in commercial software packages like Materials Studio by 3DS Biovia. Yet, multiple open source freeware codes are available as well. We tried to stick to the open source solutions to increase the accessibility of the application.

16. How relevant do you see the services for the commercial sustainability of NanoCommons? (Select just one option)

- Very
- Slightly
- Neutral
- Slightly not
- Not at all

17. How relevant do you see the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure for the sustainability of the service/TA? *(Select just one option)*

- Very
- Slightly
- Neutral
- Slightly not
- Not at all

18. Were any *social [sustainability goals](#)* addressed directly or indirectly *(e.g. through data accessibility for re-use – see here for ways [artificial intelligence supports the SDGs](#))* by the TA?
If **YES**:

o Which SDGs have been addressed? *(More than one is possible)*

SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being → *This TA application is related to the kinetics of nanoparticles and in particular the translocation rates of NPs into the blood stream, which might support novel medical research*

SDG 5: Gender Equality → If YES, why?

SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation → If YES, why?

SDG 8: Decent work and Economic Growth → If YES, why?

SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities → If YES, why?

SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities → If YES, why?

SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions → If YES, why?

SDG 17: Partnerships → *The NanoCommons infrastructure supported the collaborative research performed in this TA. Adaptation of the existing services to the requirements of the TA applicant brought the TA applicant and NTUA together.*

o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? *(Enter your answer in text form)*

The R client developed through this TA enhances the accessibility to biokinetics and QSAR models uploaded on Jaqpot and facilitates their integration in R computational pipelines, supporting and promoting global efforts on addressing safety of ENMs and risk assessment.

19. Were any *environmental* [sustainability goals](#) addressed, directly or indirectly, by the TA? If **YES**:

- o Which SDGs have been addressed? (*More than one is possible*)
 - SDG 6: Clean water and Sanitation → If YES, why?
 - SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities → If YES, why?
 - SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and production → If YES, why?
 - SDG 13: Climate action → If YES, why?
 - SDG 14: Life below water → If YES, why?
 - SDG 15: Life on Land → If YES, why?
 - SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why?
- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? (*Enter your answer in text form*)

20. Were any *economic* [sustainability goals](#) addressed, directly or indirectly, by the TA? If **YES**:

- o Which SDGs have been addressed? (*More than one is possible*)
 - SDG 8: Decent work and Economic Growth → If YES, why?
 - SDG 9: Industry Innovation and infrastructure → If YES, why?
 - SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and production → If YES, why?
 - SDG 17: Partnerships → If YES, why?
- o How might the services help NanoCommons to support the achievement of these goals on a more global scale? (*Enter your answer in text form*)

21. If you were not able to answer the last 3 questions about the *social, environmental and economic* [sustainability goals](#) that have been addressed by the TA, would you be interested in participating in an online training on how research can support the SDGs?

Yes

No

22. If you answered YES to the last question, would you be willing to pay for the offered training on utilising your research in support of the SDGs?

Yes → Enter your contact details here (Name, Affiliation, Email address):

No